

WORD FORMATION WITHIN THE FRAMEWORK OF COGNITIVE PARADIGM IN MEDICAL TERMINOLOGY

Hasanova N.

PhD student of Baku Slavic University, Azerbaijan

English teacher at Baku State University

Abstract

The article comprehensively analyzes the process of word formation in medical terminology within the framework of the cognitive paradigm of modern linguistics. The author justifies the necessity of studying terms not only as language units, but also as carriers of scientific knowledge structures with a systematic and cognitive approach. In particular, the notion of valency in word formation is brought to the fore, and morphological, syntactic and semantic relations of derivative words are investigated. The mutual influence of verb and noun roots, their derivational potential in medical terms, as well as the differences of their derivational potential based on semantic groups are shown. The article also emphasizes the influence of extralinguistic factors, for example, physiological observation possibilities and medical-humanistic values, on word formation. In the formation of medical terms, the role of the subject of the doctor, who is the carrier of knowledge, is specially mentioned. As a result, the cognitive approach allows for a systematic understanding of the linguistic and cognitive aspects of medical terminology and creates the basis for a deeper investigation of terminological models in this field.

Keywords: cognitive linguistics; medical terminology; word formation; valency; derivation; terminological system.

Introduction.

The cognitive paradigm of modern linguistic research has influenced virtually all aspects of language learning and has found its reflection in such areas as cognitive grammar, cognitive semantics, cognitive lexicology and lexicography, cognitive phraseology, cognitive derivatology, etc. Studies in the field of terminology are also conducted from a cognitive approach. The task of cognitive linguistics is to explain “the correlations and connections found between the structures of language and the structures of knowledge”. The consideration of terminology in the cognitive aspect, which has received the name of cognitive terminology, comes from the need to explain the relations between the structures of the language and special knowledge structures. A term is a linguistic (verbal) means of expressing a scientific notion and is the result of the interaction of two systems (linguistic and scientific knowledge systems). Such a systematic direction of the terminology has sufficiently justified the use of a systematic approach to its research. “*In the context of the modern scientific paradigm, systematic methods focusing on the description of terms and terminological systems are replaced by methods of cognitive modeling of terminologies aimed not only at the description of linguistic phenomena, but also at finding the reasons that explain their nature*” [4, p.124]. At the same time, the cognitive paradigm finds its application in the study of systemic phenomena as a general methodological basis of modern research.

Discussion. A number of studies are developing in the direction of “systemic cognitology”, where the ideas of philosophy and psychology about the natural cognitive processes are connected with the ideas of the system approach as a methodology of cognition [7; 8]. Moreover, the opinion is expressed that a new stage of systematic research is expected within the framework of the cognitive direction in science in general, and in linguistics in particular. The combination of systematic and cognitive approaches can be very effective in the

study of terminological word formation, primarily its structure, for a number of reasons. First, the basic notion of cognitive linguistics is the concept understood as “*knowledge of what is determined by all its connections and relations*” [10, p.100]. It contains not only the invariance of the meanings of the representative word, but also the invariance of the word-forming nest. Therefore, the analysis of the word-forming potential of the word-term denoting the concept can act as a source of information about the notion itself. Second, cognitive processes are inaccessible to direct observation, and modeling of the word-forming nest, analysis of the structure and content of derivative paradigms provides a kind of “window of access to the mental world”. Thirdly, the terms obtained as a result of the implementation of structural methods of word-forming have a transparent internal form, thanks to which they can clearly express the relation between the notions of a certain field of knowledge. “*Such terms are characterized by a clearly expressed motivation that determines their significant cognitive value*” [3, p.17]. The method of valency analysis corresponds to the goals and objectives of both systemic and cognitive approaches. “*Valency analysis is combined with many other methods of linguistic research and is well formed*” [3, p.39]. In modern linguistics, valency analysis is widely used in word formation, including in the study of terminology. The notion of linguistic valency arose as a result of taking into account the grammatical compatibility of the verb. Later it became known that valency at a high syntactic level is a manifestation of the regularities that are realized at a deep semantic level. The notion of valency in relation to the semantics of the combination of units has been decisive for the possibility of the transformation of this concept from a word combination to a word, first to a compound word, and then to a derivative lexical unit. Currently, the provisions of the linguistic valency theory are used to describe the system relations at different levels of the language, syntactically, word formation, considering the arrangement of words in

word combinations and sentences, considering the compatibility of roots and suffixes. Word formation occupies a special place among the processes of terminogenesis due to the most complete implementation of system-forming features of language. Within the term of a derivative word, paradigmatic (the inclusion of a derivative word in a derivative paradigm and a derivative model), syntagmatic (the notion of a derivative word as a “restricted syntagma”) and hierarchical relations (the relationship of the paradigm between words of the same derivation) are realized. Due to the greatest “degree of systematicity”, the clear expression of relations between concepts, the ability to clearly determine the direction of derivation, and the higher degree of probability of unambiguously determining the meaning of the term of derivative word, the formation of suffixed words is distinguished. Valency is the main thing for the implementation of potential system relations in word formation. In general, the study of linguistic valency, and in particular derivational valency as a point of intersection of syntagmatic, paradigmatic and hierarchical connections, helps to understand the systemic nature of language more deeply. “*Objects studied within the system approach are presented as models, their elements are explained as cells - empty cells that represent subjects of the subject area and are filled as knowledge is acquired*” [8, p. 46]. The metaphor of “empty cells” or “nests” has been used repeatedly and very effectively to describe linguistic phenomena. The same metaphor has been used by L. Tenier as a basis for the study of linguistic valency. Medical terminology is of particular interest from the point of view of the possibility of combining cognitive and systems approaches in research. In particular, T.V. Novikova uses the medical discourse as an example to justify the importance of integrated system-cognitive models from a philosophical point of view. She explains that the essence of the valency method consists in studying and calculating the possible combinations of a language unit with other single-level units (words in a phrase and sentences or morphemes formed by a derivative word). The word-formation valency of a root that understood as the ability of a root to form a word according to a certain derivational model, is primarily related to the part of speech to which the root belongs and is determined by the categorical characteristics of its part. Substantive nomination is the main method of nomination. The issue of recognizing a verb as a term and its role in terminology is a subject of debate. However, a systematic approach to the study of terminology and the investigation of the process of term formation allows us to classify verbs as terms. “*The verb also acts as a carrier of terminological meanings, and its role in terminology is determined by systematic word-forming relations*” [6, p.12]. Verbs often form the basis of the derivative paradigm, all of which are terms: *to irritate; irritation; irritant; irritative*. N.I. Shelkhovskaya, having studied word formation in the cognitive aspect on the material of Russian, English, German and French languages, comes to the conclusion that in the word-forming systems of these languages, there is “*an opposition and mutual law of gravitation of two poles - noun and verb*” [9, p. 9]. As can be seen from the analysis of the terminology

system, noun and verb roots act as a motivational basis for the formation of terms in medicine. The bases of these parts of speech are involved in the formation of substantives, that is, they provide the appearance of the main nominative units. Noun roots are involved in the formation of the verb, and verb roots are involved in the formation of the noun, and the presence of one formation restricts the appearance of the other. In addition, these derivative adjectival roots play an important role in the formation of word combinations and the construction of the text. Thus, the interaction of the verbal and substantive word formations meets the requirements of the terminological system in nominative units, the formations of isomorphs and the structure of the text. Based on this, it is appropriate to refer to the characteristics of the formation paradigm of verb roots, which are the motivational roots for derivative nouns, and verb roots that form the core of formation paradigms and the valency of verbs derived from it. Verbal roots in English realize their derivational potential in two substantive lines: action and as the name of the person/thing who performs the action, for example, *to inject; injection; injector*. Substantive roots realize their potential along verbal chains (*a pulse; to pulsate*), which also create substantive chains, as a result of which derivative words having the same part of speech as the word that set them in motion appear. This is especially due to the very wide categorical semantics of nouns, which is expressed by the ability to form concrete nouns from abstract nouns, for example, *nutrition - nutritionist*, or abstract nouns from concrete nouns. *Dwarf - dwarfism*, etc. However, the study of valency problems is not limited to enumerating the possible combinations of linguistic units. In order to understand the systematic nature of the language, it is also necessary to consider cases where potential valency is not realized. Such reasons can be linguistic in nature and are revealed when analyzing the language system. These reasons include: the derivative/non-derivative structure of the word root, since the terms *catheterize* (to insert a catheter); *hirudinize* (to apply leeches) are derivatives, they do not enter into word formation later; the presence of a word that has a meaning corresponding to the meaning of the potential derivative: bone - ossification (formation of bone substance); N - V: *sputum* (phlegm) - *to expectorate* (to cough with phlegm), and others. Taking into account linguistic factors affecting derivational valency makes it necessary to turn to another feature of roots that participate (or do not participate) in word formation – to word formation. “*The word-forming activity of a word root is understood as the total number of words that are together with the word in question in such semantic relations that correspond to the relation between the motivating word and its derivatives in accordance with one or another order of the derivative paradigm*” [1, p.54].

If the word formation potential is realized by word-forming means except affixation, or if it is a word that has a necessary meaning in the language system, then valency can be lower than activity. Valency can be equal to activity if all potential possible affixal means motivated by a given basis are used. However, valency can never be higher than activity. Having identified all

the linguistic factors limiting valency, it can be concluded that this or that term is not capable of forming the next term due to extralinguistic factors. From a linguistic point of view, it makes it unnecessary. Establishing the word-forming valency and word-forming activity of the root is the result of a systematic analysis, and in order to clarify the extralinguistic reasons of the word-forming activity or passivity of the root, it is necessary to turn to the cognitive analysis of the semantics of word terms. Such an analysis involves both the study of the semantics of individual words and the study of the characteristics of semantic groups, which are combinations of words based on certain relationships between individual meanings. The features of the semantics of any word can be used for the analysis of its lexical explanation, the definition of these words. As a rule, the features that arise during the combination of words in semantic groups are not reflected in lexical explanations. Grouping words in this way is possible only on the basis of involving knowledge about the relationships between notions. Thus, for example, it is quite logical to combine medical terms related to the respiratory and digestive systems into one semantic group in the form of “normal physiological processes”. Such a conclusion is made not based on the information presented in the definition, but based on knowledge about the functioning of the human body. Consequently, the features of the “linguistic behavior” of the entire semantic group are determined by some extralinguistic factors, which are determined by involving knowledge about the object. Having a “knowledge component” in such extralinguistic factors allows us to talk about their cognitive basis. Moreover, even terms belonging to the same semantic group reflect different word-forming valency. “*The analysis of such cases suggests that it is simply due to the influence of deeper reasons that determine the term’s belonging to a certain semantic group. Then, the terminological dictionary has been selected from lexicographic sources and informative books*” [5, p.180]. Thus, in particular, the verbs of the semantic group “normal physiological processes” *inhale, digest* have a fully derivative paradigm. That is, the roots of these verbs are the action names *inhalation, digestion* and participates in the formation of *inhalator; digester* with the name of inventor. Verbs of the same semantic group *to wink, to yawn* have only action names in the derivative paradigm. The actions described by the verbs of this semantic group are not the same in terms of their degree of importance for the normal life of the organism. Derivative names of verbs that describe actions related to the special functions of a certain organ and have no vital meaning are not related to the name of its inventor. Among the verb derivatives that describe normal physiological processes related to the activity of the body’s vital systems, there are names of the author, meaning “device, apparatus” *aspirator* (sucker); *respirator* (artificial ventilation of the lungs); *coagulato* (coagulant) or “drug, medicine” *salivator* (substance that stimulates salivation), the intended functional purpose of which is associated with the restoration of a vital function that has been disrupted. Most of the verbs included in the “pathological processes” semantic group do not have author names in

the derivative paradigm. Analysis of the actions described by these verbs allows us to conclude that the verbal names are “natural cause” which causes a certain pathology and the words *to vesicate* (to be covered with bubbles), *to poison* that cause this or that pathology. Otherwise, that is, when it is impossible to determine the pathological factor in principle, it is impossible to name it: *to displace* - to change the place, *to dislocate* - to remove from its place. These verbs describe the effect caused by a force that is not mediated with another substance, but exceeds the physiologically permissible load. After that, let’s consider the features of the realization of valency in noun-terms using the example of semantic groups “substances existing and produced inside the body” and “substances existing outside the human body”. The first semantic group includes the terms *saliva, urine, lymph, bile*, etc. which despite belonging to the same semantic group as the verbs mentioned above, demonstrate different word-forming activity. The nouns *saliva, urine* are included in word formation later. The verbs *to salivate; to urinate*, nouns *lymph, bile* are weakly in word formation. The potential difference in the substantive bases of a given semantic group in terms of verb order can be explained by the difference in the processes in which these substances participate. The processes described by the derivative verbs *to urinate, to salivate* are related to the excretion of substances in a normal physiological state, they are available for direct observation and are known even to non-specialists. Processes related to the function of substances defined by the terms *lymph, bile* occur inside the body and cannot be directly observed during normal physiological activity, this idea is known mainly to specialists in that field. The second group “substances existing outside the human body” is represented by such terms as *tobacco, cocaine, morphine, heparin, hirudin*, etc. Verbs formed from the nouns of the considered semantic group have the meaning “to apply what is indicated by the root for medicinal purposes”. If the substance is used for human medical purposes, then the noun denoting it has a derivative verb *hirudin - to hirudinize* (to take hirudin, to put leech); *heparin - to heparinize* (to use heparin). Other nouns, such as *hashish*, do not have derivatives in the verb row. All derivative abstract nouns have the same meaning: “source-caused poisoning”, *cobraism* is poisoning with cobra venom, *tobaccoism* is poisoning with tobacco, etc. All nouns have the meaning of “a person suffering from a disease resulting from excessive use, the source of which is indicated”: the term *cocainist* - a person who uses cocaine, *morphihst* - a person who uses morphine, *alcoholic* - a person who drinks alcohol very much. If the substance has no other effect on the body than its negative effect, then among the derivatives the corresponding noun is named only by abstract nouns with the meaning of poisoning. The nouns *hashish - hashishism* (poisoning with hashish), *heparin* and *hirudin* have been formed from verbs, since they were used in medical practice for humanistic purposes. Derivative nouns from these verbs meaning “poisoning” have not been recorded, apparently, such facts are unknown to medical science. Person names and abstract nouns are in a mutually directed derivational relationship, that is,

from person names meaning a person suffering from a disease, derivative abstract nouns denoting a state are formed, or vice versa. Moreover, if the pathological state is reflected in his appearance, the first link in the chain of word formation is the name of the person: *cretin* - *cretinism* (hypothyroidism); *dwarf* - *dwarfism* (nanism); *mongol* (a person with Down syndrome) - *mongolism* (Down syndrome). “*The analysis of the dictionary articles shows that the definitions of these terms contain a hint of a person’s appearance: e.g. mongolism - the abnormal condition of a child born mentally deficient, with a flattened skull, narrow slanting eyes, and a short, flat-bridged nose*” [2, p.102]. Down syndrome is a congenital pathological condition associated with mental retardation and is characterized by the following external signs: a flat back of the head, narrow, slanting eyes, a flat nose. If the pathological state does not manifest itself externally, the first link in the word-formation chain is abstract nouns: *amnesia* - *amnesiac* (a person suffering from memory loss); *insomnia* - *insomniac* (a person suffering from insomnia); *mania* - *maniac*. The dictionary definitions of these terms are formed according to a single model and do not include indicators of the person’s appearance. Naming of a person, which means “a person suffering from any disease”, is motivated either by a substance that causes poisoning (cocaine - *cocainist*; morphine - *morphinist*) or a state that affects personality traits (paranoia - *paranoic*; mania - *maniac*). Moreover, these terms are used to describe patients who may have a negative impact on society due to their pathological state. In this regard, it is interesting that the *International Classification of Diseases* divides these diseases into a separate category - mental and behavioral disorders, and a separate classification is compiled for them. Among such disorders are dementia and substance dependence, which are characterized by “decreased cognitive abilities and impaired social role” [5]. Thus, in order to interpret the data obtained as a result of applying the valency method, we had to turn to taking into account a number of extralinguistic factors. When explaining this, it can be said that which notions of medicine receive linguistic representation and which ones are not connected with drawing conclusions (accessibility / inaccessibility for direct observation) and interpretation (possibility / impossibility of establishing a cause-effect relationship). An axiological component is also included in the interpretation of information about the object. Relevant evaluative judgments in the study of medical terminology are: the significance of a process or phenomenon for the system: humanistic attitudes towards the human body; the effect on society due to the state of health of a person. Consideration of terminological word formation from cognitive positions dictates the need to take into account the position and goals of a person as a “cognitive subject”. In the medical field, the cognitive subject is a doctor. This point of view is reflected in medical terminology. The analysis of linguistic representations of specific notions allows to reconstruct the cognitive structures that form the basis of professional thinking.

Conclusion

The study shows that the process of word formation in medical terminology is based not only on the internal structures of the language, but also on cognitive and extralinguistic factors. The unity of cognitive and system approaches plays an important role in the formation of medical terms and the creation of semantic groups. The mutual influence of verb and noun roots, their participation in derivational paradigms reveals the deep structure of the terminological system. The derivational potential of the terms in certain semantic groups is closely related to their scientific and practical importance, level of observation and functional value. At the same time, the position of the cognitive subject as a doctor is one of the important factors influencing the formation and use of terms. Consequently, terminological word formation is not only a linguistic phenomenon, but also a reflection of the way a person perceives the world, knowledge systems and evaluation criteria. And this confirms the study of medical terminology in the cognitive aspect as a necessary and productive direction.

References

1. Belyaeva, T. M. Word-formation valency of verb stems. Moscow: Higher School, 1979. 184 p.
2. Dorlan’s Illustrated Medical Dictionary. Philadelphia – London – Toronto: W. B. Saunders, 1994. 286 p.
3. Eltsova, L. F. Concepts of space in medical terminology: abstract of diss. Cand. Philological Sciences. Ryazan, 2000. 29 p.
4. Golovanova, E. N. Introduction to cognitive terminology. Moscow: Flinta; Science, 2011. 224 p.
5. International Classification of Diseases (10th revision). Classification of mental and behavioral disorders / edited by Y. L. Nuller, S. Y. Tsirkin. St. Petersburg: Adis, 1994. 303 p.
6. Khabirova, Z. R. Dynamics of nominative processes in the formation and development of English ophthalmological terminology: author’s abstract. diss. ... candidate of philological sciences. Leningrad, 1989. 16 p.
7. Mukhacheva, N. N., Popov D. V. Systemic-cognitive approach to the formation of ontological knowledge bases of information and intellectual resources // Journal of the Ryazan State Radio Engineering University. 2009, No. 30. p. 50-57.
8. Novikova, T. V. Systemic cognitology as a method of cognition // Journal of Tomsk State University. Philosophy. Sociology. Political Science. 2010. No. 2. p. 45-54.
9. Shelkhovskaya, N. I. Verbal word formation in the cognitive aspect: author’s abstract. diss. candidate of philological sciences. Chelyabinsk, 2001. 19 p.
10. Tatarinov, V. A. History of local terminology. Vol. III. Aspects and directions of terminological research (1973–1993) Moscow: Moscow Lyceum, 2003. 408 p.